

R&D SUMMARY AND RESULTS PRESENTATION

DEVELOPMENT OF AN ENVIRONMENTALLY FRIENDLY
PLANT PROTECTION TECHNOLOGY FOR THE CONTROL
OF THE WALNUT HUSK FLY

01.04.2022 – 31.10.2024

Introduction

In recent decades, the common walnut (*Juglans regia*) has become an increasingly important fruit crop in Hungary, both economically and in terms of food safety. However, climate change and the appearance of new invasive pests—especially the western walnut husk fly (*Rhagoletis completa*)—have radically changed the conditions for walnut cultivation. While it was previously profitable to grow walnuts even under extensive conditions, plant protection has now become a key factor determining the success of production.

Walnut protection presents several challenges. The physical structure of walnut orchards, especially the large tree canopies, makes professional treatment technologically and mechanically demanding. In home gardens, where large-scale mechanized sprayers are typically not available, plant protection becomes practically unfeasible. This issue is particularly critical considering that about 85% of Hungarian households have at least one walnut tree in their garden, which could cover most of the family's annual walnut needs.

Through a grant awarded to **JELI 2000 Ltd.**, we explored the possibilities of a new, alternative plant protection technology capable of addressing these challenges: the **trunk injection method**. The aim of our experiments was to develop an effective, safe, and practically applicable technology that ensures sufficient mortality of the target pest—the western walnut husk fly—while keeping the walnut safe for consumers as a food product. Measuring pesticide residue concentrations was also essential to this effort.

Target Pest: Western Walnut Husk Fly

The western walnut husk fly originates from North America and was first detected in Hungary in 2011, in the Kőszeg region. According to its biology, it is univoltine (one generation per year), but its flight period is extended, lasting from July to late September. Early infestation may prevent proper kernel development, resulting in significant yield losses. The larvae's feeding leads to secondary infections, blackening of the husk, and reduced market value. At the orchard level, damage may reach 95%, causing a 40–50% profit loss.

The first larvae appear in early August. As they feed, brownish-purple and later black spots develop on the husk, with soft texture and irregular shape.

Methodology of Trunk Injection

Trunk injection involves introducing the pesticide directly into the tree trunk. The active ingredient then moves through the tree's water transport system (xylem, tracheae) to the canopy and developing fruits. There are several methods—active or passive, micro- or macro-scale systems, and either blade- or borehole-based application. Common to all is that they operate as closed systems, which:

- Prevent drift,
- Reduce exposure to non-target organisms,
- Lower environmental contamination,
- Minimize operator exposure to pesticides.

Several factors influence the effectiveness of injection: the chemical characteristics of the active ingredient, tree species and rootstock, xylem structure, plant health, transpiration level, and timing of the injection.

Trial Locations and Methodology

Our field experiments were conducted at several locations across Hungary and are still ongoing, including: Lengyeltóti (*Juglans Hungária*), Taksony, and Szelevény. During the trials, we used active substances such as **ivermectins**, **neonicotinoids**, **spinosad**, and **azadirachtin** in various concentrations. The developed injection tools connect to the tree trunk through boreholes of different sizes.

Sampling protocol:

- **Leaves:** 4 × 10 compound leaves per tree per sampling time.
- **Fruits:** All fruits collected from young trees; 150–200 fruits from mature trees, a few days before husk drop.
- Husk samples were cut into 4–8 parts, and a single larva was enough to consider the sample infested.
- Representative husk samples were stored at –80°C for later active ingredient analysis.

Results and Observations

Initial signs: As early as the summer egg-laying period, we observed favorable effects with **abamectin and acetamiprid**. While oviposition occurred on both treated and untreated trees, larvae on injected trees died in the early developmental stage. Only 1–2 mm dark spots appeared in the green husk, causing minimal damage.

Taksony – 2019:

In the year of injection, live larval incidence was reduced to below 10% with the lower dose (10 ml/tree), and to below 3% with the higher dose (20 ml/tree). In contrast, the incidence in control trees exceeded 90%. The abamectin concentration detected in

the pericarp was 2.45 ng/g (10 ml) and 2.41 ng/g (20 ml). However, the following year, the effect decreased, with 64% and 75% live larval incidence, indicating insufficient protection in the second year.

Lengyeltóti – 2021–2024:

Three different doses were applied, all of which demonstrated insecticidal effects. In treated trees, the incidence of live larvae ranged from 40% to 70%, while it was 100% in the control group. The active ingredient content in the pericarp showed a positive correlation with the injected dose. We used two different injection methods, but no significant difference in effectiveness was found between them.

Active ingredient content in leaves: Leaf analysis allowed us to monitor the elimination dynamics of the active ingredients.

Formulation and Analytics

Commercially available pesticides are not designed for trunk injection. Their formulations are optimized for leaf surface efficacy and often contain adjuvants that, when injected, may cause phytotoxic reactions in the xylem. For this reason, new **water-soluble (SL) formulations** were developed from existing products such as *Abamect SC* (abamectin) and *Coragen SC*. Organic solvents were used due to the limited water solubility of the active ingredients, and their phytotoxicity was assessed.

Analytical procedures:

- Measurements were conducted using validated **UHPLC-MS/MS** technique, with **QuEChERS** sample preparation.
- Analyses followed **MSZ EN 15662** standard and **SANTE (2021)** guidelines.
- We developed new sample preparation methods for walnut husk and leaf matrices.
- We also examined **metabolites** of the active substances, such as desmethyl-acetamid and various **spirotetramat** metabolites.

Conclusions

- Trunk injection with abamectin is **effective**, but provides **adequate protection only in the first year**.
- The treatment does not prevent egg-laying; larvae hatch and begin feeding, but **die shortly thereafter**.
- There is a **positive correlation** between the amount of active substance injected, larvicidal efficacy, and the concentration measured in the pericarp.
- The walnut **kernel** content of active substances **remained below the detection limit (0.0003 mg/kg)** in all cases, ensuring **consumer safety** (<MRL: 0.02 mg/kg).
- Efficacy **does not solely depend on dose**, but also on **the mobility and translocation** of the active ingredient.

- The injected compounds **do not provide sufficient multi-year protection – annual treatment may be necessary.**

Summary

Under the project led by **JELI 2000 Ltd.**, a new environmentally friendly, targeted, and food-safe plant protection technology was successfully developed for the protection of walnut trees. Trunk injection—especially using **abamectin**—may offer an effective means of control against the western walnut husk fly, applicable both in commercial orchards and home garden settings. The results of our experiments provide **new scientific knowledge** in plant protection and analytical methodology and contribute to the **development of sustainable agricultural practices** in Hungary.

Our results have been published in **two international scientific journals**:

Kiss M, Sörös C, Gutermuth Á, Ittész A, Szabó Á (2023) Avermectin trunk injections: a promising approach for managing the walnut husk fly (*Rhagoletis completa*). *Horticulturae* 9:655

Kiss, M.; Hachoumi, I.; Ladányi, M.; Nagy, V. Preliminary results about the efficacy of abamectin trunk injection against the walnut husk fly (*Rhagoletis completa*). *J. Plant Dis. Prot.* 2020,128, 333–338.

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